

ISic0633

I.Sicily inscription 0633

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

unknown

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale

interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3574 + A3575

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140732

1. Ούλπιος Νικήφορος Ἀ[ν]τιοχεύς
2. Κοίλης Συρίας τῆς πρὸς Δάφνην, ἔμπορος
3. τυχαίων (?) ἐνθάδε [—] . . ΙΗΓΑΠΟΑΙΘΑΣ
- 4.

Edition: PHI140733

1. [— — — — — — — — — — τοῦτο ἀνθρώ]-
2. πινον· τὰ θ (ε) ὦν ἐνθάδ' [ἐ]μέ; εὐψύχι, οὐδὶς ἀ-
3. θάνατος □ ταῦτα Οὐάλης μνήμης χάριν ἀνέ-
4. θηκα· ἐγὼ σέ, ἐμὲ τίς; εὐψύχι Νικήφορε, οὐδὶς ἀθάνατος.
- 5.

Edition: PHI313666

1. Ούλπιος Νικήφορος Ἀντιοχεύς
2. Κοίλης Συρίας τῆς πρὸς Δάφνην ἔμπορος
3. Τυχαίων ἐνθάδε [κείμ] αι. ἡγᾶντο ἀνθρώ-
4. πινον, τὰ θ (ε) ὦν ἐνθάδ' [ἐ]μέ. εὐψύχι οὐδὶς ἀ-

5. θάνατος □ ταῦτα Οὐάλης μνήμης χάριν ἀνέ-
6. θηκα· ἐγὼ σέ, ἐμὲ τίς. εὐψύχι Νικήφορε οὐδὶς ἀθάνατος.
- 7.

Edition: PHI333757

1. Κοίλης Συρίας τῆς πρὸς Δάφνην, ἔμπορος
2. τυχαίων ἐνθάδε [—]. .ΙΗΓΑΠΟΑΙΘΑΣ.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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